

Perception of Local Residents towards Heritage Tourism Development and Conservation: Evidence from an Emerging Economy

Samia Afrin Shetu & Akash Majumdar

Abstract

This study aims to investigate the perceptions of residents toward the development and conservation of heritage tourism based on an emerging economy, Bangladesh. The study is quantitative and exploratory in nature and has employed descriptive statistics and multivariate analysis. The researcher utilized a self-administered, close-ended questionnaire to get responses from the participants. The Nawabganj Upazila Sadar has been selected as the study area for the research purpose. The sample size for this study has been determined based on the population size of Nawabganj Upazila Sadar and the samples are selected utilizing the deliberate sampling method. The findings indicate that heritage tourism development and conservation are necessary at Nawabganj as it is enriched with attractive heritage sites. Transportation, safety and security, and authenticity are positively associated with heritage development while the attractiveness and attitude of the residents have a significant positive connection with heritage growth and maintenance. According to the perceptions of the local community, heritage tourism development has both positive and negative repercussions. So, the development of heritage tourism must be accomplished based on some criteria which will increase the positive impacts and reduce the negative externalities to the heritage tourism development. The findings and recommendations of this study will have policy implications for tourism policymakers to develop and conserve tourist sites. This is one of the pioneer studies from Bangladesh's perspective to promote heritage tourism although the paper is not out of its limitations recognized at the conclusion part of this paper.

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Introduction

Heritage plays an essential role to convey ancient values from earlier history as a proportion of the culture of a society (Nuryanti, 1996). Heritage revitalizes a perception of the period when individuals are more virtuous and had easier gratification different from today's intricate society (Squire, 1994; Timothy, 1997). Heritage tourism cannot be emerged without guaranteeing tourist satisfaction (Asmelash & Kumar, 2019). Heritage-based tourism must be developed in a sustainable way to ensure tourist satisfaction. In heritage tourism, tourist activity is not only based on the local heritage but also focuses on the formation of community identity (Ruiz Ballesteros & Hernández Ramírez, 2007). The development of tourism cannot be sustained without the help and support of the local community. Halim, Mawa, Deb, & Nafi (2022) have shown that economic, social, and political factors are significantly important for developing community-based tourism. According to Andriotis (2000), the three most important stakeholders in tourism development are locals, local authorities, and businessmen. Therefore, their perception is playing a critical role in the development of tourism in the locality. But the fact that a very trivial number of studies have focused on the perception of local people (Halim et al., 2022). This paper is an initiative to fill up this gap by assessing the perception of residents at Nawabganj, one of the renowned tourist destinations in Bangladesh. Nawabganj is one of the prominent regions in Dhaka containing many old historical buildings and Zamindar Bari. Amongst the archaeologically or historically famous buildings, the most popular ones are the residence of Khelaram (Khelaram Datar Kotha), Hasnabad Church, Braja Niketon, the Baghmara Moth and the Bakshanagar Church. The House of Harihar Ghosh, Nawabganj Ansar Camp (Painna Bari & Teli Bari), Loknath Saha's House, George's house, Lawyer's house, Cokil Paris zamindar's house, Adnan Palace, etc. are some other historical sites of Nawabganj. Nawabganj is enriched with heritage attractions and proper planning and execution of plans can make it one of the best heritage sites in Bangladesh. There are also several unpopular old buildings and many of these buildings have fallen prey to locally influential land grabbers. The Ansar & Village Defense Party (VDP), a paramilitary force of the government, have acquired some of these buildings. The House of Harihar Ghosh, the Ansar Commandant's current office which is now known as Nawabganj Ansar Camp (Painna Bari & Teli Bari), Loknath Saha's House, and a few more houses are included with them. George's house, Lawyer's house, Cokil Paris zamindar's house, Adnan Palace, etc. are also some historical sites of Nawabganj. Among those historical sites, a beautiful story has been found about Khelaram Datar Kotha (Khelaram House)

Figure 1: Old picture of Khelaram Datar Kotha (Source: ruposhi-bangla.com)

Khelaram Datar Kotha is an ancient architecture of Nawabganj that was built by Khelaram Data almost 200 years ago. A local girl Tasnim Apu shared some useful information about this historical place. She told me that Khelaram Datar Kotha is not just a name, it's a fairytale story of my childhood. Almost every night my grandmother used to tell me the history of Khelaram Datar Kotha because I was always curious about it. My grandmother mostly called it "Andhar Kotha" as it is locally known as Andhar Kotha. My grandmother said that even in the morning there was always dark inside the palace which is why they used to call it Andhar Kotha. Khelaram was born in the Dhaka district and the history of this palace is enclosed with him and his family. I heard lots of historical myths about Khelaram and his Kotha. I heard that Khelaram was very restless during his childhood and was very fascinated by the Padma River next to his house. He always wishes to float in the Padma River by boat. Although he was unsteady, he always respect his mother's decision. One day he asked for his mother's permission because he wanted to go on a voyage in the Padma River. His mother permitted him and along with the blessings of his mother, Khelaram went for trade to the Malay Peninsula. After a long time, Khelaram returned home to his mother with lots of profit. His mother ordered him to donate half portion of his earnings to the poor. He obeyed his mother's wish and donate a portion of his profit to the poor people. The poor people gave him blessings and he became famous as a Donor they named him Khelaram Data. After that Khelaram built five floor historical palace known as Khelaram Datar Kotha. I also heard that Khelaram Data used to robbery in the richest people's house and then give much of his spoils to the poor people. Some people said that there is a tunnel inside the palace which is connected with the river Ichamati and Khelaram Data is used to bringing treasure through the tunnel along the river. At the bottom of the two-story palace, the tunnel paths still exist.

Figure 2: Khelaram Datar Kotha after Rejuvenation (Source: offroadbangladesh.com)

There is another myth about Khelaram Data. He was very obedient to his mother and always try to fulfill her wishes. One day his mother wanted to eat some ripened bananas along with milk. As per her wish, Khelaram Data made a tank on the rooftop filled with pure milk and ripened bananas. He told his mother to swim in the tank and drink as much as she wish. His mother was so happy and gave lots of blessings to her son. One day Khelaram Data disobeyed his mother's decision and angered his mother. His mother was very angry that she left the palace. As soon as his mother left the palace, three floors of the palace go under the ground. After that Khelaram Data was never seen. People said that he drowned in the pond in front of his palace when searching for his mother.

Figure 3: Historical Pond in front of Khelaram Datar Kotha (Source: ruposhi-bangla.com)

There are many myths about the big pond in front of Khelaram Datar Kotha. I heard that there was a boat named "Moyorpongkhi" that was always submerged in the pond. When any needy people called for help the boat appeared and fulfill their wish. If anyone prayed for any elements such as furniture, plate, or glass in front of the pond then the boat provided those elements. There was a condition that all of the elements must be returned after finishing the occasion. One day a greedy man stole the elements he prayed for and never returned. After that, the boat never appeared. One thing that I want to mention is the actual color of Khelaram Datar Kotha was reddish but now it is colored white as it has been rejuvenated by the department of archaeology. As Nawabganj is a renowned tourism destination, more research should focus on these destinations to develop and conserve heritage sites. Moreover, there is a lack of research on heritage development based on the perception of the community in Bangladesh (Halim et al., 2022). Though few studies have been conducted in Bangladesh based on the Sundarban-based community (Dey et al. 2020; Roy, 2016), no study is performed based on the Nawabganj community. This study is an initiative to promote, develop and conserve the tourist spots at Nawabganj based on the perception study of the local respondents of this locality. Additionally, this paper will try to discover the factors affecting the development and maintenance of heritage development from Bangladesh's perspective.

Literature Review

Heritage is something that shifted from one period to another which is commonly affiliated with the word inheritance (Nuryanti, 1996). It can also be outlined in material forms like architectural and historical ruins, monuments, and antiquities on exhibition in museums as well as immaterial forms such as traditions and arts, philosophy, the festivals of great events or personality in history, unique ways of life, education stated as folklore and literature (Nuryanti, 1996; Zeppel & Hall, 1992). Heritage plays an essential role to convey the ancient values from earlier history as a proportion of the culture of a society (Nuryanti, 1996). Heritage revitalizes a perception of the period when individuals are more virtuous and had easier gratification different from today's intricate society (Squire, 1994; Timothy, 1997). Society's enthusiasm for conserving the past reflects the necessity for material objects which can assist in an appreciation of identity (Timothy, 1997; Tuan, 2001). Different features of heritage can indicate shared reminiscence of a society (Lowenthal, 1975; Timothy, 1997). For example, Independence Hall in Philadelphia and the Liberty Bell represent the collective and national heritage attractions for Americans that may inspire a well-built affectation of patriotism (Timothy, 1997). Long-term national ideals are generally represented by historical monuments on the national level as well as in western societies, national pride can be an essential

inspiration for conserving the built environment (Lowenthal, 1975; Timothy, 1997). Moreover, in the fastest-growing world, communities require recognized landmarks at the local level to stay in touch with their personal shared past (Timothy, 1997). In recent decades, the global development of tourism has introduced emerging forms of tourism (Balcar & Pearce, 1996) and tourism policies are updated to develop and attract tourist spots (Sayeda, Shet, & Rahman, 2020). Heritage tourism obtained growing emphasis in the late 1980s, and early 1990s (Balcar & Pearce, 1996). One of the vigorous areas of development in the UK and throughout the world is heritage and tourism (Millar, 1989). Heritage tourism is a recognizable sector in the growing tourism industry (Cossons, 1989). In the rapidly changing world, heritage is known as a central emerging issue in the decision-making process of how unique resources are to be utilized by the present generation or conserved for the next generation (Millar, 1989). One of the fastest-growing sectors of the tourism industry is heritage tourism which generated a strong body of literature (Chhabra et al., 2003; Garrod & Fyall, 1998; Herbert, 2001; Poria et al., 2003; Yankholmes & Akyeampong, 2010). Travelers who mostly visit cultural and historic sites mainly estimate their experience at these attractions as an additional benefit which helps to increase the possibility of repeat visits (Yankholmes & Akyeampong, 2010). Tourism products presented by the mass destinations such as the usual sea, sun, and sand (SSS) are no more appealing to the visitors and nowadays they are searching for more genuine experiences through heritage attractions (McKercher, 2002; Timothy, 1997; Yankholmes & Akyeampong, 2010). It has been accepted by many scholars that tourism-related activities by heritage tourism have been inherited (Yale, 1991; Yankholmes & Akyeampong, 2010). According to Timothy & Boyd, (2006), heritage is a combination of the past and the elements of the past used by modern days. As a subgroup of tourism, heritage tourism mainly motivates tourists for visiting a destination where there are heritage characteristics according to the tourist's perception of their heritage (Poria et al., 2006). To represent the past in the present, heritage tourism put forward many opportunities and the past can be felt following the perspective of the infinite chances of interpretation through the time and space provided by heritage tourism (Nuryanti, 1996). As heritage is a comprehensive appearance, countries like Europe have carried out the utmost use of heritage tourism and have passionate the highest effort to figure out it (Ashworth, 1994; Nuryanti, 1996). Moreover, Singapore and Hong Kong, the leading international tourism destination and traditional rivals, share a special focus on heritage which traits visible in strategic and marketing plans in the future, alongside contemporary purpose-built sights and nature (Henderson, 2002). Perception, in simple terms, can be defined as, how something is regarded, understood, or interpreted. According to Allen (1979), the terms perceived, internal, subjective, psychological, and apparent duration (time) are used interchangeably; generally speaking, they refer to the temporal value used by the subject in making his judgment. Sometimes, perception can be regarded as nothing more or less than a discriminatory response (Garner et al., 1956). In even simpler terms, the "reaction is the perception," and thus the role of the researcher is simply to determine the conditions under which a discriminatory response is obtained. These conditions then define perception (Merleau-Ponty, 2004). Unfortunately, we must agree that many psychologists who consider themselves operationists do accept this position toward perception. The topic of perception has become far more closely related to behavior than it once used to be. From a biological point of view, it can hardly be considered that the structure of perception is without its function (Broadbent, 2013). However, there are reasons for questioning whether studies related to the effects of functions on perception would be more meaningful rather than the effects of perception on other functions (Loomis & Lederman, 1986). Broadbent (2013) identified that the classical type of perception experiment is eminently suitable for fields in which all subjects behave similarly, in which the subjects possess an accurate vocabulary for describing their experience, and in which a fairly brief experience is followed by an interval in which it may be

described. But these are severe limitations, particularly the last: the closer one comes to the problems of everyday life the harder it is to stay within them (Garner et al., 1956). It then becomes necessary to set the subject to some objectively scoreable task, and to find how performance on this task is affected by various stimulus situations: this is the method used in all the experiments to be described (Broadbent, 2013). Tourism perceptions by host community residents have gained academic attention during the last decades, and their importance for planning issues, in terms of sustainable development, has been acknowledged (Lasansky & McLaren, 2004). However, there are a wide number of studies that have considerably varied in terms of theoretical bases and methodological approaches and other significant factors that have affected the development of solid foundations for further studies on resident perceptions of tourism (Cordero, 2008; Lasansky & McLaren, 2004; Liu et al., 1987). Shetu & Sayeda (2020b) have conducted a perception study on the intern students' expectations from the internship program. It is found that internship programs provide a platform to develop careers in the hospitality industry (Shetu & Sayeda, 2020a). Within the considerable body of academic research related to tourism impacts and residents' attitudes towards tourism, some models, constituting the beginning of the development of a conceptual foundation for the evaluation of social impacts (Wall & Mathieson, 2006) have been developed to help explain tourism impacts and their relationship with residents' perceptions. These models focus on the change in resident attitudes toward tourism over time (Butler, 2006; Doxey, 1975).

Tourism impacts have been commonly assessed through the examination of perceptions of host communities. Kabir & Shetu (2020) have found economic implications of tourism activity in the economy. Additionally, COVID-19 has impacted the economy largely including the tourism and hospitality sector (Karim & Shetu, 2023; Karim, Shetu & Razia, 2021; Karim & Saba, 2020). A considerable amount of literature in this field has been developed during the last few decades. Undoubtedly, one of the most significant and earliest contributions to the development of theoretical models is the one proposed by Doxey (1975) the Index of Tourist Irritation or "Irridex". The Irridex model is a four-stage theoretical model that attempts to explain host community responses to tourism development. The model recognizes that unfavorable impacts of tourism development might lead to irritation in the community. Such irritation, according to the author, is determined by the degree of incompatibility between residents and tourists. The model suggests that with the increase in the number of tourists and the development of tourist destinations, residents' perceptions vary from euphoria to apathy, then to annoyance, and finally to antagonism. Hong Kong Tourism Commission (HKTC) dedicated high emphasis on heritage as it provides an essential contribution to the attainment of objectives and a large number of tourists visit on holidays based on heritage (Henderson, 2002). Recently founded Heritage Tourism Force urged to identify archaeological and historical sites and buildings with tourism potentialities and also maintain vibrant traditions (Henderson, 2002). The relationship between tourism and identity becomes more emphasized when heritage and culture get more focus from tourists and tourist activities (Ruiz Ballesteros & Hernández Ramírez, 2007; Stebbins, 1997). The approaches of the visitors, tourist activities, and host communities are largely reconciled by local heritage in heritage tourism (Ruiz Ballesteros & Hernández Ramírez, 2007). In heritage tourism, tourist activity is not only based on the local heritage but also focuses on the formation of community identity (Ruiz Ballesteros & Hernández Ramírez, 2007). Thus two of the reference points of heritage tourism can be identity and community (Ruiz Ballesteros & Hernández Ramírez, 2007). Heritage tourism cannot be emerged without guaranteeing tourist satisfaction (Asmelash & Kumar, 2019). Heritage-based tourism must be developed in a sustainable way to ensure tourist satisfaction. It can be both a gift or a despise according to the nature of its development (Asmelash & Kumar,

2019; Hall et al., 1993). Heritage tourism should deliver a reasonable level of tourist satisfaction and it must pledge a momentous experience for them (Asmelash & Kumar, 2019). It will attract tourists to visit repeatedly as well positive perceptions tourists will share positive feelings with individuals whom they meet (Kozak & Rimmington, 2000). Tourist satisfaction helps in guaranteeing the long-term sustainability of tourist sites (Asmelash & Kumar, 2019). The development of tourism cannot be sustained without the help and support of the local community (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2015; Siamak & Hall, 2018). Local community support is largely dependent on the nature of the impacts that cause the development of tourism (Andereck et al., 2005; Rasoolimanesh et al., 2017; Siamak & Hall, 2018). The development of tourism can exert both positive and negative effects on the local community (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2017; Sharpley, 2014). The positive impact of tourism development can largely encourage residents to support its further development, on the other hand, if they perceive negative impacts toward tourism development, it will reduce their level of support for tourism development (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2015; Siamak & Hall, 2018). Several benefits can be created for the local community with the subsequent inflow of tourists in the heritage site, such as increasing income, generating employment opportunities, improving public infrastructure and facilities, promoting local culture, and preserving cultural identity (Andereck et al., 2005; Rasoolimanesh et al., 2017). On the other hand, residents can face lots of negative impacts along with the increasing number of tourists to a heritage site such as causing overcrowding and traffic congestion, increasing rate of crime, and raising cost of living (Látková & Vogt, 2012). Nawabganj is one of the famous heritage tourism sites with many natural and cultural tourist attractions. To develop heritage tourism in Nawabganj, perceptions of both the local community and tourists need to be identified. But no studies have explored it yet and there lack of research on community-based tourism development (Halim et al., 2022). To fill the study gap, the author conducted the study in Nawabganj. This study investigates the perceptions of tourists and residents toward the development and conservation of heritage tourism. Moreover, the positive and negative perception among tourists and residents regarding their support for heritage tourism development has been examined in this study. Furthermore, factors affecting the development of heritage are also determined in this study which is unique in the literature.

Research Objectives and Research Questions

The main objective behind the research work is to assess the perception of inhabitants towards heritage tourism development and maintenance. To identify the impacts of heritage tourism development and conservation on the local community, a questionnaire is developed, and data are analyzed to assess the implications. Additionally, this paper will try to identify the determinants of heritage site development in Bangladesh. Furthermore, the positive and negative aspects of tourism development will also be investigated to attract heritage tourists to this place.

Research Methodology

Study Area Description:

The research has been completed based on Nawabganj, Dhaka. The Nawabganj Upazila Sadar (Kalakopa Union, Bakshanagar Union, Barrah Union, and Jantrail Union) has been selected for collecting the necessary information to fulfill the research objectives. The study area is shown below in Map 1.

Map-1: Nawabganj Upazila

Methods for Data Collection

As the research is a descriptive study, the method for data collection is done by the survey method. The required data for the survey has been collected by making questionnaires. The questionnaires have been designed for the residents of Nawabganj Upazila Sadar and 17 questions have been asked to the local people. The data of the questionnaires of the residents have been gathered through face-to-face communication with the local people as well as through sending questionnaires on social media such as Facebook, What's app, etc. This method has been used for the data collection because questionnaires provide a sequence of asking questions. All the questions that need to be asked are designed sequentially in the questionnaire forms.

Population Size and sample

The population sizes for the study are the population of Nawabganj Upazila Sadar (Kalakopa Union, Bakshanagar Union, Barrah Union, and Jantrail Union). The total population of the selected unions of Nawabganj Sadar Upazila is 85088 (Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS), 2015). The deliberate sampling method is used to collect the data. In deliberate sampling, the population is selected from the knowledge about the population and study. The population for this report has been selected within the knowledge of the population size of the Nawabganj Upazila Sadar (Kalakopa Union, Bakshanagar Union, Barrah Union, and Jantrail Union). So, the deliberate sampling method is appropriate in this study. The sample size is calculated below.

$$n = \frac{z^2 * p * q * N}{e^2(N-1) + z^2 * p * q}$$

$$= \frac{(1.96)^2 * 0.02 * 0.98 * 85088}{(0.05)^2(85088 - 1) + (1.96)^2 * 0.02 * 0.98}$$

z= 1.96
 Confidence Level= 95%
 P=0.02
 q(1-p)= 0.98
 Error (e) = 0.05
 N= 85088

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{3.8416 * 0.02 * 0.98 * 85088}{(0.0025 * 85087) + (3.8416 * 0.02 * 0.98)} \\
 &= \frac{6406.73159}{212.792795} \\
 &= 30.1078408
 \end{aligned}$$

The sample size for the residents of Nawabganj Upazila Sadar is 30

Types of Data

This report will be based on two types of data: primary and secondary. The primary data for the research has been gathered through conversations with the local people as well as by conducting surveys online from the local people. The secondary data for the research has been gathered from different articles, books, and journals that are available online. Not only online sources have been used for this purpose but also the official records of the government have been used.

Data Analysis Method:

After collecting all the primary and secondary data from various sources, the data has been analyzed. The study is quantitative in nature and has employed different descriptive statistics like mean, minimum value, maximum value, and standard deviation and multivariate analysis to interpret the results. The results are presented through tables, charts, and graphs. In the research, Microsoft Excel, and STATA have been used to analyze the data. To determine the factors affecting heritage growth in Bangladesh, the following model is developed:

$$HDC_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Transp_i + \beta_2 Safety_i + \beta_3 Authent_i + \beta_4 Atti_i + \beta_5 Attract_i$$

Here,

HDC_i = Heritage development and conservation measured by residents' opinion

$Transp_i$ = Transpiration facilities and conditions to visit heritage

$Safety_i$ = Safety at the tourist's spot

$Authent_i$ = Authentic heritage site rather than an artificial one

$Atti_i$ = Attitude of the residents of the destination

$Attract_i$ = Attractiveness of the tourist site

Detailed Data Analysis

Demographic profile of the respondents

In this section, the data that have been collected from the local people of Nawabganj, Dhaka is analyzed. The data have been gathered through face-to-face interviews. The method of this research is quantitative and for this purpose, face-to-face interviews have been selected. From the total population, 30 residents have been taken as the sample size. The data analysis part is based on these 30 residents of Nawabganj. In the first phase, the demographic data of the residents of Nawabganj has been shown using different graphs and their percentages have also been discussed.

Table 1: Demographic profile of the respondents

Demographic profile	Total	
	Number	%
Gender:		
Male	19	63%
Female	11	37%
Age		
Below 20 years	3	10%
21 – 30 years	13	43%
31 – 40 years	11	37%

Above 40 years	3	10%
Marital Status		
Married	21	70%
Unmarried	9	30%
Occupation		
Teacher	1	3%
Student	8	27%
Service holder	10	33%
Businessman	5	17%
Others	6	20%
Educational Level		
Primary/High school	2	7%
SSC or equivalent	4	13%
HSC or equivalent	9	27%
Graduate	12	40%
Post-graduate	3	13%
Income Range		
Below 10,000	9	27%
10,000-20,000	6	23%
20,000-30,000	9	30%
30,000-40,000	2	7%
Above 40,000	4	13%

The male respondents were 19 and 11 female respondents participated in the survey. Both males and females were interested to share their thoughts about their local destinations as well as the local facilities. Both of them were friendly in performing their interviews. Maximum numbers of the respondents were from the age range of 20-30 and the least 10% were from the age range below 20 years as well as the age range 40 years above. About 37% of respondents were from the age range of 30-40 years. Most of the respondents in the age range of 20-30 were very responsible, supportive, and well-known about the facts that are happening in Nawabganj. Most of the respondents are service holders with a percentage of 33% and the least number are teachers with a 3% ratio. The owners of grocery shops, dispensary shops, and transportation services fall into the category of a businessman. The government service holders as well as the employees who work in the private sector fall into the criteria of service holders. About 17% of respondents are businessmen, about 27% of respondents are students and about 20% of respondents are from other different occupations such as housewives, farmers, etc. Most of the respondents are Graduates with a percentage of 40%, and the second largest educational qualification of the participants is H.S.C level with a percentage of 27%. The lowest educational qualification of the participants is Primary/High School level with a percentage of 7%. Both the percentage of Post Graduate Level and S.S.C level is 13%. Most of the local people earn 20000-30000 taka per month on average. The second highest income range of the people is below Tk. 1000 on average per month. About 23% of people earn 10000-20000 taka per month on average. About 7% of people earn 30000-40000 taka per month on average and 13% of people earn above 40000 takas per month on average.

Perception of residents of Nawabganj toward heritage development

Table 2 summarizes the key statistics of the respondent's perception of the tourism spots at Nawabganj. Most of the respondents believe Nawabganj is one of the top tourist spots. Transportation facilities are good enough to visit the places and there is security concern at the tourist places at Nawabganj. According to the responses of the local people, about 73% of respondents strongly agree that authentic tourism attractions are preferable to artificial attractions. About 20% of the respondents agree with them. On the other hand, 7% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree with that statement.

Table 2: Perception of residents about Nawabganj tourist destinations

Questions	Mean	Min	Max	SD
Nawabganj is enriched with heritage attractions.	4.67	3	5	0.66
Transportations facilities are quite good at Nawabganj	4.46	2	5	0.93
There is no safety and security related problem at Nawabganj	4.33	1	5	1.12
Authentic tourism attractions are preferable to artificial attractions.	4.66	3	5	0.60
Nawabganj has the potential to become one of the best heritage sites in Bangladesh.	4.60	3	5	0.67
More attention needs to be given to the development and conservation of the heritage sites of Nawabganj.	4.8	3	5	0.48

Figure 4: Potentiality of tourism development at Nawabganj

According to the responses of the 30 local people, most of the local people strongly agree with the statement that “Nawabganj is enriched with heritage attractions” and on the other hand, none of the tourists disagree with the statement. About 13% of the local people agree with the statement. On the other hand, 10% of local people neither agree nor disagree with the statement. Most of the local people strongly agree with the statement that Nawabganj has the Potentiality to Become One of the Best Heritage Tourism Destinations in Bangladesh and on the other hand none of the tourists disagree with the statement. About 20% of the local people agree with the statement. On the other hand, 10% of local people neither agree nor disagree with the statement. Most of the respondents of local people, with a percentage of 83%, strongly agree that the heritage sites of Nawabganj need to be developed and conserved. About 13% of the local people agree with them. On the other hand, 3% of the local people neither agree nor disagree with the statement.

Determinants of heritage tourism development and conservation

In this section, a model is developed to determine the determinants of developing and conserving heritage tourism. Table 3 summarizes the results of the factors affecting the development of heritage tourism. Transportation and safety are positively associated with heritage promotion. Additionally, authentic tourism destinations are highly attractive to tourists, and they affect the development of tourism as well. Furthermore, the attractiveness and attitude of the residents of the heritage are significantly positively associated with the development of tourism destinations.

Table 3: Factors affecting heritage tourism development and conservation

HDC	Coef.	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Trans	.043	.082	0.53	.604	-.216	.13	
Safety	.06	.05	1.19	.252	-.046	.166	
Authent	.212	.245	0.86	.4	-.306	.73	
Att	.551	.245	2.25	.038	.035	1.068	**
Attract	.344	.175	1.97	.065	-.024	.713	*
Constant	-.564	.485	-1.16	.262	-1.587	.46	
Mean dependent var		4.565	SD dependent var			0.728	
R-squared		0.908	Number of obs			23	
F-test		33.570	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		6.745	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			13.558	

*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

Findings and Discussion

In this study, the researcher highlights the perception of the people of Nawabganj towards heritage tourism development and Conservation. According to the analysis of collected data, the researcher found that most of the inhabitants who participated in the study are male, highly educated, and young shown in table 2. The reason that may be obvious in terms of locals' demographic profile might be that the male respondents feel more interested in this study regarding heritage tourism development rather than the female and the young aged local people are more interested and have more chances in sharing their knowledge about heritage sites of knowledge rather than old, aged people. Besides, it can be said that the educated locals feel more interested to share their knowledge about heritage sites in a particular destination because they might be curious to share their knowledge about the heritage history of Nawabganj. The study found that Nawabganj is enriched with diverse heritage attractions which is also agreed by the local people. The researcher of the study also tried to identify inhabitants' perceptions of the tourists who visit Nawabganj. According to the survey, the local has a perception that the young tourist of Nawabganj is more problematic than other aged tourists. The reasons behind these negative perceptions might be that the young generation mostly focuses on enjoyment rather than thinking about others' disturbances. According to the survey, the researcher identified that the resident is much concerned about the development as well as conservation of heritage sites in Nawabganj and they believe that Nawabganj has lots of potential to become one of the famous heritage tourism sites in Bangladesh. Factors that affect the development of tourism includes transportation facility, safety, authenticity, attractiveness, and the attitude of the residents. Apart from these, the researcher also tried to identify local communities' perceptions of impacts based on the development of heritage tourism in Nawabganj. According to the responses of local people, the researcher identified that there are a lot of positive impacts of heritage tourism development and conservation at Nawabganj.

Figure 5 shows the positive implications of heritage development at Nawabganj based on the opinion of the respondents. They said that it creates employment opportunities and generates their income source which in turn increases their standards of living. Some of the respondents said that tourism development ensures better infrastructural development. It also creates awareness about protecting and preserving cultural heritage and helps to promote it to the next generation.

Figure 5: Positive impacts of heritage tourism development

Figure 6: Negative impacts of heritage tourism development

Figure 6 demonstrates the negative aspects of tourism development. Heritage tourism development also imposes negative impacts that are founded by the researcher with the help of surveys on local communities. The study found that tourism development causes overcrowding, traffic jam, noise, and pollution and increases the price level of local commodities. It also raises the cost of living. Besides, demonstration effects also took place among the local community as they try to lead them as like a tourist. It also affects biodiversity by ignoring the standard carrying capacity of a particular site. The study also identified that; the development of tourism also causes an increasing number of crimes in the tourist area. However, heritage development also has negative consequences. Figure 6 demonstrates the negativities of heritage conservation.

The findings of the study can be utilized as a practical guideline. It will help tourism practitioners and Destination Management Organizations (DMO) to introduce effective strategies to successfully develop heritage tourism in Nawabganj. Moreover, the findings of the study will also help to utilize the positive impacts of heritage tourism development on the local community and reduce the negative impact by implementing proper strategies. By reducing the identified negative impacts, DMOs can easily develop heritage tourism at Nawabganj and can promote it with the help of local communities.

Recommendations and Conclusion

The researchers of the study have tried to achieve the research objectives by conducting a descriptive analysis. For obtaining the objectives, the researcher has collected the necessary data by surveying the selected samples. After collecting data, the researcher tried to accumulate some findings by analyzing those data. The findings indicate that heritage tourism development and conservation are necessary at Nawabganj as it is enriched with attractive heritage sites. Sound transportation facilities, security at the tourist sites, authentic tourism destinations, attractiveness of the tourist spots, and the attitude of the local people are important factors in developing community-based tourism in Bangladesh. Nevertheless, the development of heritage tourism must be based on some criteria which will increase the positive impacts and reduce the negative impacts shown in the discussion part. The ways of conservation must be concerned about its authenticity maintenance according to local people's preferences. According to the study findings, the researcher has recommended some guidelines that can be considered for effectively developing and conserving heritage tourism at Nawabganj. Heritage tourism must be developed sustainably by ensuring effective management and conservation of cultural and historic heritage sites. Income from tourism sites must be utilized properly for supporting heritage tourism development. Awareness must be created among the local community. High priority needs to be given to the creation of jobs for locals that are stable, permanent, and full-time, and that provide fair salaries and benefits. Public-Private Partnership needs to be developed to effectively develop strategies for heritage tourism development at Nawabganj. Cultural richness can be strengthened and interpreted through developing interpretative programs and events based on the heritage and distinctiveness of the area; furnishing in tourism establishments, local cuisine in restaurants, traditional designs in architecture, and art and sculpture in public spaces; conceiving creative, sensitive, and viable visitor attractions where local culture and traditions can be showcased. Proper carrying capacity needs to be identified for the heritage site for reducing overcrowding and ensuring sustainable development. A website can be developed by emphasizing heritage tourism and it must be updated along with necessary information from time to time. The website must have significant information about the heritage sites of Nawabganj. Heritage tourism sites of Nawabganj should be marketed through direct and indirect distribution channels such as tour operators, travel agencies, and media to effectively reach the comprehensive marketplace and for making a desirable profit. Furthermore, transportation facilities, safety, and security should be improved. Last but not the least, the residents should come forward with a positive attitude to develop and maintain the heritage sites. The study is unique to the point that it has filled up the literature by identifying the research gap in community perception-based studies. The paper has brought real pictures to light the perception of local people toward tourism development. The problems and prospects of heritage development are discovered along with the factors affecting the development and conservation. Furthermore, recommendations are suggested to promote tourism. By utilizing these recommendations, tourism practitioners and stakeholders can initiate long-term strategies for developing and conserving heritage tourism at Nawabganj and position Nawabganj as a famous heritage tourism site among tourists. However, the paper has several limitations. It has covered only Nawabganj as the targeted tourism site, more tourism

destinations can be taken with more respondents in future studies. Additionally, policymakers can be taken as the respondents to develop a friendly tourism policy toward heritage development. A mixed method-based study can also be employed to reveal a more conclusive result.

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